

A Review on Machine Learning Methods for Decision-Making in Resource and Production Planning

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Abstract. Modern manufacturing environments require decision support systems (DSSs) that can adapt in real-time to dynamic conditions and increasing data volumes. Traditional DSSs, often based on rule-based models, fall short in delivering the flexibility and resilience required for efficient resource and production planning. Meanwhile, machine learning (ML) offers promising capabilities for forecasting and autonomous optimisation, yet its applications in manufacturing remain fragmented and lack systematic consolidation. This work provides a structured overview of applied and validated ML methods in resource and production planning, linking specific industrial use cases to individual techniques. The majority of existing research has concentrated on production scheduling, demand forecasting, candidate identification, and predictive maintenance. By contrast, areas such as disruption management, joint optimisation (e.g., performance prediction combined with scheduling), and energy consumption forecasting remain underexplored. Following Kitchenham’s systematic literature review methodology, this study aims to systematically identify, evaluate, and synthesise machine learning approaches applied in real-world resource and production planning, providing both a practical guideline for selecting suitable methods and a structured foundation for understanding their evolution over time. Future research should prioritise the practical implementation of the identified methods across diverse industrial sectors to validate their effectiveness and scalability in real-world settings. Particular attention should be given to areas such as energy consumption forecasting, joint optimisation, and disruption management.

Keywords: Decision Support · Machine Learning · Resource Planning · Production Planning.

1 Introduction

Decision support systems (DSSs) have improved the manufacturing processes by providing a framework for managing decision-making procedures. DSSs address structured, unstructured, or semi-structured problems by incorporating various

technology elements, such as databases and model management, with integrated artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, including rule-based and machine learning (ML) [29]. These systems provide extensive data analysis, reporting, and planning tools to improve human experts' ability to make faster and better-informed decisions. DSS has also been incorporated into various technologies, such as manufacturing execution systems, enterprise resource planning, advanced planning systems and business intelligence [12].

Although traditional DSSs are commonly applied, they struggle to adjust to the complex and dynamic manufacturing environment. The introduction of AI allows for automation, smart data analytics, and adaptive learning processes, which have increased the capabilities of DSSs [29,12]. The biggest advantages of AI-driven DSS for Industry 4.0 are that it enables big data processing to provide real-time insights and predictive analytics [57]. This has made it possible for decision support tools to become personalised and forward-looking, which is especially important in flexible manufacturing systems [12] and maintenance [57].

Current manufacturing environments require DSSs that can adapt to dynamic conditions and handle increasing data complexity. Traditional DSSs often rely on static models, failing to provide the flexibility and resilience necessary for efficient production and resource planning. For instance, management systems that enable real-time monitoring and configuration changes when equipment fails or disruptions occur, helping to mitigate the impact and restore normal operations [24]. While ML methods provide predictive insights and autonomous optimisation, their application in manufacturing remains fragmented, as it is scattered across isolated use cases without consistent or standardised approaches. Addressing this limitation is crucial to help researchers and practitioners identify and apply the most effective ML methods to evolving manufacturing scenarios.

This review aims to connect academic research with practice by presenting the ML methods deployed for decision support in resource and production planning. These domains are compelling due to their common importance across various enterprises. The study adopts a systematic literature review methodology following Kitchenham's guidelines, which involves a structured process of identifying, selecting, and synthesising studies on ML applications in these areas [31]. The work addresses the following research question:

What is the extent and distribution of different ML algorithms used to support decision-making in resource and production planning within manufacturing environments?

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of resource and production planning, along with DSS applications in manufacturing. The literature review process is detailed in Section 3. Section 4 presents articles classification based on ML categories and algorithm types, while Section 5 addresses specific industrial scenarios. Section 6 depicts a discussion of the findings, followed by conclusions in Section 7.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Resource and Production Planning

Resource and production planning are critical components of manufacturing management that support various aspects such as resource allocation, task scheduling, and maintenance coordination to achieve efficient and cost-effective production. Resource planning involves determining and managing the materials, labour, inventory management, and equipment necessary to meet production targets, while production planning focuses on designing optimal production processes, including energy consumption, scheduling, and quality [14,4,47].

Effective planning ensures that manufacturing systems can adapt to demand fluctuations, minimise operational costs, and improve overall productivity. Recent advancements have integrated data-driven approaches, such as ML, to enhance decision-making processes by predicting demand, optimising resource allocation, and improving production efficiency [13,48]. The increasing complexity of manufacturing environments, driven by digitalisation and globalisation, has intensified the need for sophisticated planning tools that can respond dynamically to changing conditions [60,10,68].

2.2 Decision Support Systems in Manufacturing

One of the early works regarding DSS in manufacturing dates back to the 1980s when Cynthia K. Whitney (1985) shed light on the control issues that flexible manufacturing systems face [64]. Following in the 1990s, there were significant advancements and applications in software development for manufacturing processes. This included an exploration of computer-integrated manufacturing, which supported real-time resource allocation decisions [18]. Additionally, research focused on human-computer interactions in knowledge acquisition and interfaces of process planning systems [26].

Developing leaner and more responsive computer-integrated DSS systems started in the 2000s by addressing the technology, organisation, and personnel to automate decision-making during the earliest stages of manufacturing [2]. Further, efforts were made to capture and disseminate human expertise related to interventions on production lines, enabling factory-wide information sharing for enhanced defect management [15]. This progression marked a shift towards integrating human contributions more effectively within the system. In 2010, the constraint theory was introduced in DSS and applied to demand-pull inventory management, which helps users determine buffer management parameters. In this tool, users could simulate and explore various combinations of inventory status by utilising the DSS's modules [27]. This period overlapped with the early emergence of Industry 4.0 concepts, as the increasing adoption of cyber-physical systems and the internet of things (IoT) began to shape DSS capabilities toward more responsive, data-driven production and resource planning systems [39].

In the 2020s, DSSs in manufacturing are increasingly characterised by a multifaceted approach that addresses various aspects of the manufacturing process.

These include production planning within complex manufacturing systems [8], multi-agent manufacturing execution systems enhanced by embedded AI [40], IoT-based DSS [25], cloud manufacturing solutions [55], web-based tools with integrated AI [58], and real-time data analysis [11]. Additionally, the application of digital twins in manufacturing DSSs has been explored by incorporating diverse modelling methodologies into a systematic decision-making framework [41,30]. This decade is marked by a combination of advanced technologies, including IoT, AI, ML, and data mining, which contribute to more informed and faster decision-making. In this context, there is a growing need for the development and implementation of data-driven solutions in DSS.

3 Review Process

This study adopts a systematic literature review methodology following the guidelines proposed by Kitchenham [31]. The review process comprised four stages: database search, study selection, data extraction, and synthesis of findings.

3.1 Database Search

The literature search is organised around four groups of keywords. The first group addresses the overall objective of the system, focusing on "*decision support*" and "*decision-making*". The second group examines the level at which decisions are made, including "*resource planning*" and "*production planning*". The third group considers the decision-making environment, covering areas such as "*manufacturing*", "*fabrication*", "*production*", and "*assembly*". Finally, the fourth group highlights applied methodologies, including "*machine learning*", "*deep learning*", and "*artificial intelligence*". Each group was connected using the "*AND*" operator, and each category within the groups was connected using the "*OR*" operator. Searches were conducted in Scopus, Web of Science, and IEEE Xplore due to their comprehensive coverage of manufacturing and ML research, including high-impact journals and peer-reviewed conference proceedings. The review focused on publications from 2010 up to mid-2024 to capture recent advances in ML applications for resource and production planning.

3.2 Study Selection

Figure 1 illustrates the process of systematic literature review. After removing duplicates, inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied, yielding 45 relevant studies. The abstract screening, full-text screening and data extraction were independently performed by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved through discussion to ensure consistency.

Studies were included if they:

- Addressed ML applications supporting decision-making in production or resource planning.

- Were published as peer-reviewed journal articles or conference papers in English.
- Reported experimental validation with clear performance metrics.

Studies were excluded if they:

- Were review articles, to focus on original research.
- Lacked experimental validation or testing to ensure methodological rigour.
- Were non-English publications or grey literature, due to accessibility and quality concerns.

Fig. 1: Flowchart depicting the systematic literature review process.

3.3 Data Extraction and Synthesis

Data extraction focused on identifying the ML methods applied, evaluating use case suitability, and confirming validation of these methods. All extracted data were systematically organised in a structured spreadsheet to ensure traceability and facilitate analysis. Extracted data were categorised by ML method, algorithm type, and linked to specific industrial scenarios in production and resource planning. Additionally, the number of selected papers published per year was reported to provide temporal context. Separate analyses were conducted to examine the distribution of methods within production planning and resource planning domains, followed by an overview of the challenges addressed in both areas. The findings were synthesised to highlight trends and gaps in current research.

4 ML Methods in Resource and Production Planning

This section presents a classification of selected research articles based on their allocation to specific ML categories and algorithm types (see Table 1). The categorisation is divided into supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning (RL), with each category further subdivided according

to the applied algorithm type. Supervised learning primarily includes regression, classification, and time series prediction algorithms. As time series prediction is crucial to real-time applications, a separate category was created for these applications. Unsupervised learning is mainly represented by clustering approaches. RL encompasses algorithm types, including Q-learning, policy optimisation, model-based methods, and multi-agent systems.

Table 1: Selected articles and their allocation to ML category and algorithm type.

ML category	Algorithm type	Source
Supervised learning	Regression	[28,1,14,34,51,62,63,3,4,32,7,52]
	Classification	[20,37,49,6,38,45,66,47,22,61]
	Time series prediction	[42,61,21,46,53]
Unsupervised learning	Clustering	[32,51]
	Clustering	[51,19,43,50,16]
Reinforcement learning	Q-learning	[63,56,44,35,33,65,36,16,23,17]
	Policy optimisation	[5,62,63,9,59,68,33]
	Model-based	[67,54]
	Multi-agent	[69]

Figure 2 illustrates the yearly distribution of research articles selected for this review, covering the period from 2011 through mid-2024. The data reveal a clear upward trend in publications, especially from 2019 onwards. Note that the count for 2024 is lower compared to 2023 because it only includes publications up to mid-year. This temporal overview helps contextualize the evolving research interest and activity within the field.

Fig. 2: Trend of research article publications by year.

Figure 3 further contextualises these findings by displaying the allocation of various ML methods across production and resource planning. The diagram illustrates the frequency with which different learning categories were applied

to these domains, highlighting the associated algorithm types. The width of the bars indicates the frequency of different ML algorithm types used. This visualisation supports the identification of both widely adopted and underexplored ML methods. For example, production planning tends to shift towards supervised learning, indicating a greater reliance on forecasting and predictive control. In this context, regression is primarily utilised for resource planning, whereas classification algorithms are more frequently explored in scenarios related to production planning.

Fig. 3: Overview of ML methods applied in production and resource planning.

5 ML Applications in Industrial Use Cases

This section presents a comprehensive mapping of applied ML algorithms to the identified use cases within resource and production planning. It highlights how these diverse approaches are tailored to address specific manufacturing requirements, enabling more effective decision-making and operational efficiency across different industrial scenarios.

5.1 Production Planning

Table 2 provides an overview of identified industrial use cases in production planning along with the ML algorithms applied to address each specific challenge. The use cases encompass a wide range of manufacturing scenarios such

as cost estimation, scheduling, disruption management, and performance prediction. A complete list of abbreviations for the algorithms used can be found in Appendix A.

Table 2: Use cases, ML algorithms, and sources.

Use case	ML algorithm	Source
Candidate identification	BDTR, MLP, LR, DFR, BLR, Logit, LDA, KNN, DTC, NB, SVM	[66,46]
Cost estimation	ENR, RF: R, GBR, RR, Lasso, LR, PR, KNN: R, DTR, M5P	[1]
Cost optimisation	KBR, DTC, Logit	[53]
Energy-consumption forecasting	MLP	[47]
Cycle time prediction	MLP	[45]
Material requirements planning	RL: SARSA	[35]
Parameter estimation	LR, GDR	[6,7]
Performance prediction	ANFIS, ANFIS-PSO, ANFIS-GA	[28]
Performance prediction and cost optimisation	robust regression, LASSO, AR(1), K-Means	[51]
Performance prediction and production scheduling	ANN	[22]
Production scheduling	CNN, K-Means, RL: D3QPN, RL: DQN, RL: A2C, RL: PPO, MARL	[42,16,59,65,36] [69,68,16,23,9,56]
Production scheduling and resource allocation	MLP, iResNet, ResNet, LSTM, SAE	[61]
Disruption management	HCA, LSTM	[50,3]
Supply chain management	DTR, RL: LSTD	[21,54]
Joint optimisation (production planning, maintenance, quality)	RL: R-SMART	[44]

Part or assembly candidate identification plays an important role during the early conceptual design stage for additive manufacturing [66,46]. In the domain of cost estimation, advanced regression methods help manufacturers better predict energy usage and production costs, targeting sustainability and competitiveness in industries such as steel production [1]. Similarly, in a plastic products manufacturing, soft computing models that incorporate fuzzy logic rules and ML methods have been used to analyse production data from manufacturing execution systems, providing more precise cost estimates and supporting strategic decisions on shift scheduling [53].

Energy-consumption forecasting in job shop systems has also benefited from the implementation of ML methods. For instance, multilayer perceptrons (MLP) have demonstrated strong performance in predicting total energy consumption for different orders [47]. In the textile industry, MLPs improve the accuracy of cycle time predictions over traditional statistical approaches, particularly when managing complex relationships among multiple variables [45]. Demand-driven material requirements planning is one of the production planning methods that effectively prevents stockouts while minimising on-hand inventory [48]. To opti-

mise its parameters a RL approach was employed using the state–action–reward–state–action (SARSA) algorithm [35].

Other research has combined ML with model predictive control to develop a low-complexity approach that estimates unknown parameters from biased decision-making data through regression analysis [6,7]. This approach enables decisions which aim to maximise net profit in collaborative industrial production planning. For performance prediction in integrated solar combined cycle power plants, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFIS) have been applied, along with particle swarm optimisation (PSO) and genetic algorithms (GA), to further refine predictive accuracy. The presented study shows highly accurate results in the performance prediction of hybrid thermal power plants, making it a valuable tool for designers, energy managers, and decision-makers [28].

Combining performance prediction with cost optimisation has also gained attention. For example, robust regression and clustering methods have been used to enhance existing models for production planning, supporting companies to balance cost and performance goals more effectively [51]. Similarly, artificial neural networks (ANNs) have proven valuable in production scheduling by predicting future performance metrics, such as makespan, under varying production conditions. This enables real-time adjustments to production plans and supports more responsive manufacturing operations [22].

Production scheduling itself is one of the most extensively studied areas. Recent work has used discrete-event simulation to generate realistic training data for ML models [42]. RL approaches, including deep Q-networks (DQN) [65,36,16,23], advantage actor-critic (A2C) [9], and proximal policy optimisation (PPO) [59,68], have also shown promise in developing adaptive scheduling systems. Emerging research has explored integrated models that address both production scheduling and resource allocation by applying neural networks, residual networks (ResNet), and recurrent architectures such as long short-term memory (LSTM) networks and stacked autoencoders (SAE) [61]. A proposed model integrates the strengths of ML in feature extraction and multi-classification, making classification decisions based on the resource demand histogram to improve production management efficiency.

Disruption management is another important area where ML plays a significant role. One study applied hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) to manage disruptions in mixed-model continuous production. It supports real-time decision-making by anticipating disruptions, identifying relevant information, and generating response strategies [50]. Additionally, ML-based predictive maintenance was applied to forecast disruptions on the shop floor. Researchers compare various strategies, including proactive approaches, by incorporating feedback from actual failures to adjust future planning. Their work also presents the integration of ML predictions to minimise total weighted tardiness and improve customer service in an Industry 4.0 context [3].

Supply chain management has also seen innovative applications of ML. For example, regression trees combined with fuzzy inference systems have been used to create interpretable models that can handle uncertainty and automatically

generate decision rules based on production data and managerial expertise [21]. Another approach connects decision layers operating at different time scales using RL to solve complex Markov decision process problems embedded within mathematical programming, supporting multi-period decision-making in dynamic supply chains [54]. Finally, for the purpose of joint optimisation, some researchers have developed an RL framework to coordinate production planning, maintenance, and quality management simultaneously. In this use case, optimal policies for RL were derived through agent-based modelling, leading to more balanced and resilient manufacturing systems [44].

In summary, supervised learning techniques, such as regression models and neural networks, have significantly improved the accuracy of cost estimation, energy forecasting, and cycle time prediction. Neuro-fuzzy systems enhance robustness when dealing with uncertain or incomplete data. RL facilitates dynamic, real-time scheduling with resource allocation in complex and changing environments. Clustering methods and predictive maintenance approaches help anticipate and manage disruptions. Additionally, hybrid models that combine statistical and soft computing techniques improve decision-making in supply chain operations. Together, these advancements demonstrate that integrating ML methods into production planning can drive greater efficiency, flexibility, and competitiveness in modern manufacturing systems.

5.2 Resource Planning

In the domain of resource planning, five distinct use cases have been identified. The defined use cases and corresponding applied ML methods are presented in Table 3. The list of abbreviations and their full forms can be found in Appendix A.

Table 3: Use cases, ML algorithms, and sources in resource planning

Use case	ML algorithm	Source
Demand forecasting	MLP, SVR, RF: R, ERNN, LR, KNN: R, LASSO, BN, K-Means, ELM, NNAR	[38,37,20,43,19,32]
Predictive maintenance	Bi-LSTM, CNN, SVR, DTR, XGBoost, MLP, LR, RF: R, RL: Beta-Bernoulli, RL: DQN, RL: A2C, RL: PPO, RL: TRPO	[67,17,14,34,63,33]
Predictive maintenance and demand forecasting	RF: R, RL: PPO	[62]
Resource allocation	MLP, RF: R, ERT, GLM, GBM, RL: AC	[49,52,5]
Inventory management	RBFNN	[4]

Demand forecasting remains one of the most extensively researched areas within resource planning. In the automotive industry, for example, a case study explored an automotive manufacturer’s demand forecasting process, aiming to propose an appropriate forecasting tool and assess its implementation prospects.

The results showed that the algorithm based on extreme learning machine (ELM), a type of feedforward neural network, provided the most accurate predictions and added the most value to the forecasting process [32]. Another study from the automotive industry introduced a multivariate approach for multi-step demand forecasting. It was developed to predict manufacturer demand throughout a component's lifecycle, showcasing the versatility and precision of ML in addressing the challenges of demand prediction in assembly manufacturing [20]. Comparative studies between ML and traditional demand forecasting methods in the textile industry offer valuable insights for strategic demand planning and medium-term decision-making [38,37]. In the fast fashion sector, neural networks have been used to predict weekly demand for a wide range of products, generating accurate forecasts that feed into a digital twin to optimise resource allocation and operational planning [52].

Implementation of unsupervised learning involves customer segmentation through the k-means clustering algorithm [43]. This algorithm categorises customers based on purchasing data such as order history and recency, frequency, and monetary analysis, resulting in an optimisation approach that achieves higher customer satisfaction and increased profits compared to traditional models. Another example of k-means implementation considers grouping daily customer orders into representative clusters based on similarities in demand patterns [19]. This approach compressed historical data into a smaller set of characteristic demand patterns, enabling more efficient simulation experiments and improved decision-making for production planning.

Predictive maintenance is another significant application area for ML in resource planning. Combining temporal and spatial attention modules with bidirectional long short-term memory (Bi-LSTM) networks and convolutional neural networks (CNN) has enabled researchers to develop adaptive models for remaining useful life prediction [14]. This approach supports predictive maintenance by estimating the health and lifespan of machinery, aiding in maintenance planning and reducing the risk of failure. To minimise unexpected downtime and optimise tool usage in milling operations, researchers have also investigated linear regression (LR), support vector regression (SVR), decision tree (DT), random forest (RF), extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), and MLP models [34]. Another research focuses on optimising production and maintenance decisions by learning yield rate behaviours during the decision-making process, particularly under uncertain demand and equipment degradation [67].

RL has shown considerable promise in optimising maintenance scheduling. One study applied an RL agent to determine the optimal timing and type of maintenance actions, balancing production efficiency and maintenance costs to improve output and reduce disruptions [17]. Similarly, RL techniques have been used to coordinate post-prognostic demand management, production planning, spare parts inventory, and maintenance activities for single-machine systems, demonstrating their flexibility [63]. Comparative research further highlights that RL techniques can outperform traditional rule-based heuristics in order dispatching and maintenance management, achieving higher machine utilisation rates

and improved throughput times for order dispatching [33]. Considering maintenance management, RL algorithms reduce failures, maintenance actions, and costs while increasing the number of finished orders compared to reactive and time-based maintenance strategies. In a related scenario, predictive maintenance has been integrated with demand forecasting by using a regression algorithm to estimate machine health conditions, providing decision-makers with more accurate information [62].

Automated machine learning (AutoML) methods have also been applied to address complex tasks. For instance, one study utilised an AutoML tool to predict key decision variables, including lead time, production time, waste generation, and delivery delays, in garment manufacturing. This approach supported a broader optimisation module designed to minimise production costs and cycle time through more effective subcontractor allocation [49]. In mining operations, RL algorithms have been implemented to dynamically allocate shovels to different mining areas based on operational requirements, while clustering methods define diglines by grouping spatially connected mining blocks with similar processing characteristics. This adaptive framework aims to maximise financial returns by enhancing operational efficiency in copper extraction [5]. The ML method has also contributed to advancements in inventory management. One study utilised a radial basis function neural network (RBFNN) to model variable demand and design an environmental hedging point policy, helping organisations maintain resilient inventory practices amid demand uncertainty [4].

In summary, ML methods in resource planning address diverse industrial challenges. Neural networks improve demand forecasting in the automotive, textile, and fast fashion sectors. Deep learning supports predictive maintenance by estimating machine health and reducing downtime, while regression and decision trees optimise production under variable demand. Clustering methods like k-means improve customer and demand segmentation for targeted planning. Furthermore, RL boosts maintenance scheduling, spare parts management, and equipment allocation, often surpassing traditional heuristics. AutoML and RL frameworks increasingly assist production planning and asset deployment in industries from garment manufacturing to mining. Together, these approaches help manufacturers manage demand uncertainty, enable real-time optimisation and integrate dynamic maintenance planning.

6 Discussion

The chronological advancement from 2011 to 2024 saw a clear shift towards ML methods. Earlier years leaned heavily on static prediction tasks using regression models for cost estimation and quality prediction. In contrast, more recent trends emphasise real-time adaptability and intelligent decision-making, especially through adopting RL. This shift reflects the growing need for dynamic systems capable of adapting to rapidly changing industrial environments, such as those influenced by supply chain disruptions or fluctuating market demands. Additionally, hybrid and ensemble approaches, such as adaptive neuro-fuzzy in-

ference systems and boosted decision trees, indicate a deliberate effort to enhance predictive accuracy and robustness by combining multiple techniques. These hybrid models are valuable in complex scenarios where single models may fail to capture the intricate relationships among variables. The research in resource and production planning reflects a robust and growing dependence on ML to address the multifaceted challenges of modern industrial systems. The progression from regression-based models to advanced RL methods underscores the increasing complexity and dynamism of production environments.

7 Conclusion

This systematic review maps the current landscape of ML applications in decision support for resource and production planning within manufacturing environments. By categorising studies according to ML methods and industrial scenarios, the review provides a comprehensive answer to the research question regarding the extent and distribution of ML algorithms in this domain. The findings reveal a clear trend toward increased adoption of RL techniques, reflecting a shift toward real-time adaptability and intelligent decision-making capabilities. Additionally, there is growing interest in joint optimisation approaches that integrate production planning, maintenance, and product quality aspects to address multifaceted industrial challenges. Despite these advances, gaps remain in certain critical areas. Notably, research on energy consumption forecasting and joint optimisation scenarios requires further exploration to effectively balance operational efficiency, sustainability, and cost objectives. Overall, this review underlines the evolving landscape of ML in manufacturing decision support and provides a foundation for guiding future research toward addressing complex, multi-dimensional challenges in resource and production planning.

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A Appendix: List of Abbreviations

Table 4: List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Name
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
ANFIS-GA	ANFIS with Genetic Algorithm
ANFIS-PSO	ANFIS with Particle Swarm Optimisation
AR(1)	First-order Autoregressive Model
AutoML	Automated Machine Learning
BDTR	Boosted Decision Tree Regression
BLR	Bayesian Linear Regression
BN	Bayesian Networks
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DFR	Decision Forest Regression
DTC	Decision Tree Classifier
DTR	Decision Tree Regression
DSS	Decision Support System
ELM	Extreme Learning Machine
ENR	Elastic Net Regression
ERT	Extremely Randomized Trees
FCN	Fully Connected Network
GBM	Gradient Boosting Machine
GBR	Gradient Boosting Regression
GLM	Generalized Linear Model
GDR	Gradient Descent Regression
HCA	Hierarchical Cluster Analysis
IoT	Internet of Things
iResNet	Improved Residual Network
KBR	Kernel Bayes Rule
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbors
KNN: R	K-Nearest Neighbors Regression
LASSO	Lasso Regression
LDA	Linear Discriminant Analysis
LR	Linear Regression
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
Logit	Logistic Regression
M5P	M5 Model Tree Regression
MARL	Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
NB	Naive Bayes
NNAR	Neural Network AutoRegressive
PR	Polynomial Regression
RBFNN	Radial Basis Function Neural Network
ResNet	Residual Network
RF: R	Random Forest Regression
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RL: A2C	Reinforcement Learning: Advantage Actor-Critic
RL: AC	Reinforcement Learning: Actor-Critic
RL: Beta-Bernoulli	RL closed-form Beta-Bernoulli model-based method
RL: D3QPN	Reinforcement Learning: Double Dueling Deep Q-network with Prioritized replay and Noisy networks
RL: DQN	Reinforcement Learning: Deep Q-Network
RL: LSTD	Reinforcement Learning: Least Squares Temporal Difference
RL: PPO	Reinforcement Learning: Proximal Policy Optimisation
RL: R-SMART	Reinforcement Learning: R-SMART
RL: SARSA	Reinforcement Learning: State-Action-Reward-State-Action
RL: TRPO	Reinforcement Learning: Trust Region Policy Optimisation
SVM	Support Vector Machine
SVR	Support Vector Regression
XGBoost	Extreme Gradient Boosting